

ADVANTAGES OF USING PEDAGOGIC METHODS IN TRAINING STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: in this article, thoughts and views are expressed about the formation of verbs in elementary grades and giving students an understanding of this. This article is relevant as it provides both theoretical and practical instructions about the methods that will help pedagogues closely in this process.

Key words: verb phrase, formation, addition, change, program, education, foreign experience, method, tool.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, words that express action and state are words belonging to the verb group, and they have the following characteristics:

1. Has a lexical meaning;
2. Has a time category;
3. Has the person-number category;
4. Has the ratio category;
5. Has a category of inclination;
6. It turns out;
7. Has the property of making.
8. Has a modal form;
9. It has partitive and partless forms.

But not all of the above specific features are revealed in the process of teaching the verb group to elementary school students. Because it is required that every given information corresponds to the student's level of understanding.

The national program for the fundamental reform of the educational system and its development developed by the Republican Education Center envisages the formation of an understanding of the following features of the verb group in primary school students:

1. The lexical meaning of the verb phrase (implies what kind of question the answer will be);
2. Some simple information about the tense category of the verb group (only one or two examples of past, present, future tenses);
3. Participial and non-participial forms of the verb group (participial verbs expressing the completion of an action, verbs expressing the non-completion of an action - participle verbs; the basis of participle verbs in forming the unpartitioned form);
4. Forming a verb phrase (only by means of the affixation method);
5. Some information about the ratio category.

The verb word group has the same formation feature as other independent word groups. Words related to the word group of verbs are mainly formed by means of two methods:

1. Affixation (method of forming a word by adding a word-forming suffix to a word);
2. Composition (formation of a new word from the addition of two bases, that is, a word).

In linguistics, a word belonging to the verb word group can be formed by adding a word-forming suffix from the following word groups:

1. Horse;
2. Quality;
3. Hip;
4. Pronoun;
5. Exclamation;
6. Imitation;
7. Modal.

This method is also called morphological method in linguistics. By adding the following special suffixes to the above-mentioned independent and intermediate word groups, words related to the verb word group are formed using the morphological method:

1. -a affix: with the help of this suffix, a word related to the verb group is created from independent word groups such as nouns and adjectives, and intermediate word groups such as imitation. For example, the verb "tuna" is formed by adding the suffix -a to the base of tun (which is a noun). The verbs qiyna, yasha, ata are among them.

2. -r (-ar) affix: with the help of this suffix, new words of the verb group are created from the words of the adjective group. For example, -r is added to the old adjective (it is added depending on the base of the word: if the base of the word ends with a vowel, -r; if the base of the word ends with a consonant, add the suffix -ar) forms the verb eskir;

3. -y (-ay) affix: with the help of this suffix, a word belonging to the verb word group is made from independent word groups such as adjectives and adverbs. For example, the verb ulg'ay is formed when the suffix -ay is added to the adjective ulug';

4. -sira affix: noun with this suffix. verbs are made from independent word groups such as adjectives and pronouns. For example, the verb suvsira is formed when the suffix -sira is added to the word "water". The words yotsira and sensira are among them.

5. The suffixes such as -la, -illa, -uvla, which we should pay attention to, are nouns, adjectives, pronouns, adjectives, and verbs from word groups that are taken separately such as taqlid and exclamatory words. makes words related to word groups.

The compositional method of creating new words is also known as the syntactic method in linguistics. It is formed in the process of combining the bases of two, sometimes more, words. Verbs in this group are divided into the following two groups according to the word groups they are made of:

1. Noun and verb;
2. Verb and verb.

The process of forming a verb as a result of adding a suffix to the words of the above-mentioned word groups is not fully taught to elementary school students. The national program envisages giving elementary school students an understanding of how to make words related to the verb group using only the affixation method.

MAIN PART

Elementary school students do not learn step by step information about the formation processes of the verb phrase using the affixation method. This process corresponds to the 3rd stage (class) of primary classes based on the requirements of the national program. Until then, students should have the following information about the verb phrase:

1. Basically, the lexical meaning of words related to the verb word group;
2. Some knowledge, skills and abilities about the tense category.

Pupils begin to learn the features of the formation of verbs in the section "Fairy Tales-Leaders to Goodness" of the 3rd grade mother tongue and reading literacy textbook.

In this period, attention is mainly focused on words related to the verb word group formed with the following suffixes:

1. -la;
2. -illa;
3. -ulla.

When these suffixes are added to words of other word groups to form verbs, there are some changes in the structure of the base, and these changes are also consciously explained to the students. These changes are observed especially during the addition of suffixes -illa and -ulla. In parallel with this process, students' pronunciation is also worked on. For example, it is appropriate to reveal this in imitation words that are part of intermediate word groups:

1. Shov+illa=shovulla: in this word, under the influence of consonant v, the suffix -illa changes, and the vowel i changes to u.
2. The same phenomenon is observed in the composition of the verb Guv+illa=guvulla.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the process of learning the verb vocabulary, primary school students pay special attention to the construction of the verb. In this process, their vocabulary and oral speech develop at a high level. Students learn to make words belonging to the verb word group from words belonging to other word groups. However, it should be noted that, as mentioned above, students are not given an understanding of all the methods of making. It is advisable to organize this process based on innovative methods by each pedagogue based on his skills.

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